

Picture Your Microbiome: A Simple At-Home Tool for Instant Gut Health Insights

Donghyeok Lee¹, Ecem Yuksel², Huy Ngo¹, Roy Montijn¹, Remco Kort², Evgeni Levin^{1*}

¹ HORAIZON Technology BV, Delft, Netherlands

² Amsterdam Institute for Life and Environment, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Amsterdam, The Netherlands

*Corresponding Author: Evgeni Levin, Email: evgeni.levin@horazon.nl

Abstract

The human gut microbiome is key to health, yet the standard methods for composition profiling (e.g., sequencing) are slow and expensive. We present a noninvasive method that infers microbiome features from smartphone-based photographs of fecal smears, taken by participants at home with minimal equipment. Distinct from prior studies that relied on a single device or operator, our work leverages a large and heterogeneous image dataset collected across diverse smartphones and users, ensuring broad applicability. Our models accurately identified several genus-level abundances, alpha diversity indices, the Metagenomic Aerotolerant Predominance Index (MAPI) and a newly defined butyrogenic-to-aerotolerant (B/A) ratio. External validation in three independent disease cohorts confirmed the B/A ratio as a generalizable marker of gut dysbiosis. Robustness analyses showed that the model was resilient to moderate image perturbations and that its decisions were not influenced by external confounding factors. These findings demonstrate that smartphone-based fecal imaging can serve as a fast, practical surrogate for microbial profiling, thereby enabling personalized nutrition in at-home settings and supporting large-scale studies without relying on extensive sequencing.

Introduction

The human gut microbiota represents a dynamic and densely populated ecosystem of bacteria, viruses and eukaryotic microorganisms that collectively exert a significant influence on host physiology, metabolism, immune homeostasis and overall health [1]. Disruptions in the equilibrium of this intestinal community (commonly referred to as dysbiosis) have been implicated in a broad spectrum of chronic diseases, ranging from inflammatory bowel diseases and metabolic syndrome to neuropsychiatric disorders and malignancies [2]. Among the many factors shaping the composition and functional potential of the gut microbiome, diet stands out as one of the most potent and important modulators, with specific interventions (such as enhanced dietary fiber consumption or increased intake of fermented foods) shown to elicit reproducible shifts in microbial diversity, short-chain fatty acid production and host inflammatory markers [3].

Traditionally, comprehensive characterization of the gut microbiota has relied upon stool collection followed by culture-independent sequencing-based approaches, including 16S ribosomal ribonucleic acid (rRNA) gene amplicon profiling and shotgun metagenomics. While these methodologies offer granular taxonomic resolution and functional insights, they remain time-intensive and dependent on specialized laboratory infrastructure and bioinformatics expertise [4]. Consequently, conventional sequencing workflows are ill-suited for real-time monitoring or large-scale epidemiological studies. This limits their applicability in contexts where rapid or at-home diagnostic assessment of gut microbial status would be advantageous.

Recent advances in computer vision and machine learning have raised the possibility of inferring microbial community characteristics directly from digital images of fecal samples. In a recent study involving nonhuman primates, Maaskant et al. [5] demonstrated that deep learning models trained on paired fecal smear images and metagenomic sequencing data could accurately predict the relative abundance of major bacterial genera (including critical butyrate-producing taxa). They also showed robustness to various image perturbations and variations in how fecal samples are smeared. Building upon this concept, subsequent work in a multi-ethnic human cohort extended the approach to 16S rRNA gene-based profiles. The SMEAR (Smartphone Microbiome Evaluation and Analysis in Rapid-time) study achieved high accuracy for some of the 50 most prevalent genera and for overall alpha diversity, relying solely on smartphone-captured fecal smear images [6].

Motivated by these promising directions, we have recently conducted the Gut Health Enhancement by Eating Favorable Food (GEEF) randomized controlled trial (RCT). Healthy adult volunteers were randomized to high dietary fiber (HDF), high fermented food (HFF) or control (CG) diets over an eight-week intervention period [7]. The GEEF protocol incorporated rigorous longitudinal collection of fecal samples, dietary logs and participant-generated fecal smear images at multiple time points. Participants were instructed to capture high-resolution images of standardized fecal smears using their own smartphones, accommodating a wide range of device models, resolutions and camera sensitivities. As a result, for the first time we assembled a large and heterogeneous image dataset. Unlike prior studies that relied on a single device or operator, our dataset offers a more realistic and generalizable foundation for training image-based microbiome prediction algorithms.

A unique aspect of our work lies in predicting interpretable gut health indices. The gut microbiome comprises a multitude of bacterial taxa that can be categorized not only by taxonomy but also by functional roles, which often better reflect their impact on host physiology than taxonomic labels alone. Butyrate producers are of particular interest because key short-chain fatty acids serve as the primary energy source for colonocytes and strengthen epithelial barrier function. In addition, they exert anti-inflammatory effects through histone deacetylase inhibition and activation of G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) such as GPR41 and GPR43 [8,9]. In contrast, aerotolerant taxa often expand when luminal oxygen levels increase, a condition commonly linked to intestinal inflammation and gut dysbiosis [10]. Elevated oxygen favors the growth of facultative anaerobes and aerobic pathogens such as *Salmonella* and certain *Escherichia coli* strains, while simultaneously suppressing beneficial strict anaerobes, including butyrate producers [10].

To quantify the balance between butyrate-producing capacity and aerotolerant prevalence, we computed a newly defined butyrogenic-to-aerotolerant (B/A) ratio. This ratio was defined as the sum of relative abundances of all butyrate-producing genera divided by that of aerotolerant-associated genera. The specific genera classified into each functional group are detailed in Table S1. A higher B/A ratio indicates an enrichment of butyrate-producing taxa and reduced luminal oxygen levels, which are associated with stronger resilience against inflammation, dysbiosis, and pathogen-driven disturbances. The ratio-based metrics provide biologically meaningful indicators of gut health than individual taxa alone [11], as they capture shifts in microbial balance. The biological validity and cross-cohort generalizability of the B/A ratio are evaluated in independent disease datasets and discussed in the Discussion section. Other examples where ratio indices proved to be interpretable include the Bacillota/Bacteroidota ratio, the gram-positive/gram-negative ratio, the Prevotella/Bacteroides ratio and the Fusobacterium nucleatum/Faecalibacterium prausnitzii ratio [11].

To further assess gut microbiome health, we employed MAPI, a single summary score that quantifies whether aerotolerant or strictly anaerobic bacteria predominate in the gut, with higher values indicating a more dysbiotic, oxidative environment. This is a quantitative metric defined as the

natural logarithm of the ratio of relative abundances of aerotolerant to strict anaerobic bacterial species. In the foundational paper by Million and Raoult [12], MAPI was defined and validated using sequencing of the V3–V4 variable regions of the 16S ribosomal ribonucleic acid (rRNA) gene in 70 individuals of varying age, geography, and nutritional status. The term “metagenomic” in the index name refers broadly to sequence-based community profiling rather than specifically to whole-genome shotgun metagenomics. Million and Raoult demonstrated a significant dose-dependent relationship between fecal redox potential and MAPI calculated from 16S rRNA gene amplicon data (linear regression, $R^2 = 0.17$, $p = 0.0004$), establishing the biological validity of the index in this context. Furthermore, MAPI has since been applied to 16S rRNA gene amplicon data in independent studies. Kort et al. [13] calculated MAPI from sequencing of the V4 variable region of the 16S rRNA gene in a cohort of 139 Ugandan children using the same database of prokaryotic aerotolerance classifications published by Million et al. [14]. Their analysis revealed differences in MAPI between language-impaired and non-impaired children, further supporting the applicability of the index to amplicon-based data. The MAPI calculation is performed primarily at the genus level, and aerotolerance is generally conserved within genera. Therefore, the MAPI score is not expected to change substantially with species-level resolution, except for *Bifidobacteria*, where species-level aerotolerance classification is applied. Accordingly, this approach is appropriate for our 16S rRNA data.

Whereas the B/A ratio reflects the functional capacity of the microbiome to maintain gut protection through butyrate production, MAPI characterizes the gut’s ecological state. A positive MAPI score indicates a predominance of aerotolerant species, often associated with gut dysbiosis and conditions such as malnutrition, inflammatory bowel disease and antibiotic-induced microbiome disruptions. In contrast, a negative score reflects a higher abundance of strict anaerobes, which are typically characteristic of a healthy gut microbiome [15]. MAPI’s utility lies in its ability to serve as a diagnostic and monitoring tool, capturing shifts in gut redox potential that reflect microbial imbalances. For instance, overgrowth of aerotolerant species such as facultative aerobes has been observed in dysbiotic states following antibiotic treatment or in severe malnutrition. This shift correlates with reduced levels of beneficial anaerobes like butyrate-producing *Clostridia*, which are critical for gut homeostasis [15]. By providing a single interpretable score, MAPI enables rapid assessment of gut health at the genus level, offering insights into microbial functionality and facilitating targeted interventions for restoring a healthy gut microbiome.

Our objectives were fourfold. First, we aimed to determine whether fecal smear images could be used to predict key microbiome features, including high versus low bacterial genus abundance and alpha diversity metrics (Shannon and Chao1). Second, we evaluated the potential of these images to predict healthy gut indices, specifically the B/A ratio and MAPI. Third, we tested model robustness by applying a series of controlled perturbations to the images, including Gaussian blur, Gaussian noise, scrambling and erasing. These experiments were designed to assess the model’s sensitivity to changes in image quality and structure and to ensure that predictions were based on biologically relevant features rather than spurious artifacts. Lastly, beyond univariate feature analysis, we applied Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA) to investigate associations between the image and microbiome datasets.

Results

Genus Classification Performance

Figure 1 illustrates the classification performance across 48 bacterial genera. Each bar represents the mean area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) with error bars indicating the standard deviation. The background color gradient reflects qualitative performance categories: AUC > 0.75 is considered Excellent (green), > 0.7 as Very Good (light green), > 0.65 as Good (yellow), > 0.6 as Moderate (orange) and > 0.5 as Poor (red). The highest performing genera included *UCG-002*, *Christensenellaceae R-7 group*, *NK4A214 group*, *UCG-005*, and *Eubacterium coprostanoligenes group*, whereas *Collinsella* and *Eubacterium eligens group* showed the weakest performance. Overall, 4 genera fell into the Excellent category, 7 into Very Good, 15 into Good, 10 into Moderate and 11 into Poor.

To further investigate the predictability and genus-level characteristics, we examined the relationship between AUC scores and the mean and variance of genus abundance using scatter plots with Pearson correlation. Figure 2a and 2b show no significant association between model performance and either mean ($r = 0.14$, $p = 0.456$) or variance ($r = 0.12$, $p = 0.512$) of genus abundance. These results show that no significant association was observed between prediction performance and genus abundance. This suggests that the model learns image-derived features regardless of abundance, making it robust and generalizable across genera.

Diversity Indices

Figure 3 shows the AUC metrics for Shannon diversity (left) and Chao1 richness (right) alongside the results of permutation tests assessing statistical significance. Shannon indices ranged from 2.1 to 5.3 (median: 3.8, interquartile range (IQR): 3.4–4.1) while observed amplicon sequence variant (ASV) counts ranged from 75 to 312 (median: 191, IQR: 158–225). The model achieved an AUC of 0.76 for both Shannon diversity and Chao1, indicating a relatively strong ability to distinguish between high and low diversity samples. Permutation tests for both analyses revealed p -values < 0.05.

To investigate the relationship between stool consistency and gut microbial diversity, fecal samples were visually examined. Figure 4 shows representative images of two distinct stool types: a dense, compact stool with a rough, clumpy surface indicative of low moisture (left), and a wetter, more fluid fecal sample characterized by a smoother surface and visible moisture (right). Consistent with previous findings, stools with lower moisture content and compact texture corresponded to higher microbial diversity, while wetter and more fluid stools were associated with lower diversity. This pattern aligns with known physiological relationships where faster intestinal transit times lead to reduced microbial diversity and increased stool water content, whereas slower transit times promote a more stable and diverse microbial community [16].

Gut Health Indices

For predicting the B/A ratio and MAPI, the model achieved AUCs of 0.78 and 0.73, respectively. Permutation tests of these analyses revealed p -values < 0.05 (Figure 5).

Robustness Tests

To evaluate the model’s robustness and potential reliance on confounding visual features, we performed perturbation-based tests as shown in Figure 6. While Gaussian blur is deterministic, the other perturbations are inherently stochastic. Therefore, we repeated each stochastic intervention 10 times and reported the average AUC score for each perturbation level. Under Gaussian blur and Gaussian noise (Figure 6a), model performance gradually declined as the perturbation strength increased. The AUC dropped more sharply with blur compared to noise, indicating that fine-grained image details are critical for the model’s predictions. This suggests that resolution plays a key role in maintaining model accuracy and highlights the importance of applying a consistent resolution filtering step when evaluating new data. For the scramble and erase interventions (Figure 6b), performance remained

relatively stable under mild alterations. However, the AUC decreased as the perturbation level increased. This implies that the model is not influenced by the global structure disrupted by smearing methods or by empty spots on the image. In the end, extreme interventions may remove meaningful visual cues from specific image regions and reduce predictive performance.

As shown in Figure 7, erase results in the most substantial changes in latent features across all degrees of perturbation, followed by Gaussian noise. In contrast, Gaussian blur and Scramble preserve more of the original feature structure, especially at lower degrees. This suggests that different augmentation types impact the learned representations to varying extents, with erase introducing the strongest feature-level shifts. Notably, the perturbation strength of Gaussian blur is relatively mild compared to others, but its effect on model performance is the most pronounced. This implies that Gaussian blur affects the image less overall but alters key predictive features that are critical for the model's decisions.

Multi-view Analysis via CCA

Figure 8 reveals a Pearson correlation of 0.51 between the first pair of canonical variates (I_1 and M_1), indicating a notable relationship between microbiome composition and image-derived features. Key microbial taxa (such as *Haemophilus*, *Faecalibacterium*, and *Akkermansia*) were among the strongest contributors on the microbiome side. On the image side, the majority of important features originated from vit_base_patch16_224_dino, including Features 2107, 2632, 646, 2327, 2625, 2252, 2207, 2411, 2642, 2296, and 2605. Additional contributions came from vit_base_patch16_clip_224 (Features 1864 and 1892), vit_large_patch16_224.augreg_in21k_ft_in1k (Features 1467, 1281 and 1507), and vit_tiny_patch16_224 (Features 1222, 934, and 73). No features from resnetv2_50x1_bit_distilled appeared among the top 20.

Figure 9a projects individual data points onto the first canonical variates, revealing a strong linear relationship between views. A permutation test confirmed the significance of this association ($p < 0.01$). As shown in Figure 9b, canonical correlations decrease across higher-order variate pairs, though the first three remain statistically significant.

Discussion

The rising demand for at-home microbiome testing reflects growing interest in accessible personalized gut health monitoring to inform dietary and therapeutic decisions. Traditional microbiome testing kits involve collecting fecal samples, mailing them for deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) sequencing and waiting weeks for detailed microbial profiles. Although these kits deliver in-depth insights, they are expensive, time-intensive and dependent on laboratory facilities. On the other hand, using our tool one could photograph standardized smears and immediately receive feedback on microbial diversity or the gut health status. Such rapid, noninvasive assessments would enable real-time tracking of dietary interventions, allowing clinicians to tailor fiber or probiotic regimens dynamically to optimize butyrate production and ameliorate dysbiosis without the delay and cost of sequencing.

Recent studies have explored AI-integrated smart toilet systems for fecal monitoring. However, none of them have explicitly studied the link between fecal images and microbiome composition. For instance, the smart toilet developed at Stanford utilizes pressure sensors, motion detectors and deep learning algorithms to classify stool according to the Bristol Stool Form Scale (BSFS) [17]. Similarly, researchers at Duke University created a toilet system that captures post-flush stool images to classify stool form and detect blood, achieving over 80% classification accuracy [18]. The study by Zhou et al. [19] applied artificial intelligence to classify stool consistency according to BSFS using global morphological features such as aspect ratio, convexity, lumpiness, and fragmentation. This suggests that the global fecal shape that is not seen in the smeared images might enhance the model prediction in our case. Nevertheless, unlike these toilet-integrated systems, our method does not require specialized infrastructure or embedded hardware. By leveraging smartphones and low-cost smear templates, this approach is more scalable and immediately deployable across diverse environments. Standardization via templates also helps reduce environmental confounding (e.g., background), thereby increasing model robustness and reproducibility across users and settings. The additional distinction is that our approach directly predicts microbiome-related features rather than the BSFS.

Due to its scalability, our approach can be applied to large epidemiological cohorts or resource-limited settings where sequencing infrastructure is scarce. For instance, frequent smear image collection could help track microbiome changes over time during diet shifts, antibiotic use, or disease progression. Integration into telemedicine platforms and smartphone apps could make gut health monitoring widely accessible, helping people join citizen science projects and quickly spot signs of dysbiosis or disease. In addition, personalized nutrition programs could use immediate image-based feedback to improve adherence and optimize dietary choices based on individual microbial responses. For example, the technology could provide instant feedback on gut responses to new foods such as fermented products or fiber supplements, helping to support motivation and adherence. Such real-time monitoring fits well with precision nutrition, where diet recommendations are adjusted to a person's microbial profile instead of general guidelines.

Several limitations of this study should be acknowledged. First, we evaluated a binary setting based on the top and bottom 25% of samples. Although this design was useful for detecting significant differences, it excludes the intermediate 50% of the cohort and therefore does not reflect the full range of variation present in realistic clinical settings. Second, to eliminate confounding color artifacts such as blue-dye muffins, we converted all images to grayscale. While this enhanced the detection of textural features, it also removed potentially valuable color information such as bile pigments or subtle dietary dyes. Previous research has demonstrated that the characteristics of biological samples are associated with the microbiome [20]. Future research should explore the use of selective color channels (e.g., red-green luminosity) or multispectral imaging to complement texture data without introducing confounders. Third, our robustness tests did not cover all types of real-world imaging artifacts, such as salt-and-pepper noise [21], uneven lighting or lens distortion common in smartphone cameras. Although our results indicate resilience to moderate noise, broader evaluation against a wider spectrum of imaging conditions will be necessary for clinical translation.

Additionally, although the GEEF study included diverse dietary habits, it was limited in terms of geography and ethnicity, consisting primarily of adults from the Netherlands. To ensure our findings are generalizable, further validation in multi-ethnic and geographically varied populations (such as those from Asian or African regions) is crucial. Furthermore, the lack of biological interpretability in our model restricts our ability to provide trustworthy explanations for the results, which is critical for clinical acceptance and broader applicability. Future work should prioritize improving biological insight to better understand the mechanisms underlying the predictive features and to strengthen confidence in the model's generalizability.

More diverse health indices could also be employed to facilitate monitoring of microbiome-associated health status. Several indices have been proposed, such as the Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes ratio and the *Fusobacterium nucleatum*/*Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* ratio. However, the Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes ratio has shown inconsistent associations with obesity and other health conditions across studies [22], while the *Fusobacterium nucleatum*/*Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* ratio requires species-level resolution that is not available in our current dataset. More recently, the Health-Associated Core Keystone (HACK) index [23] was introduced, which ranks microbial taxa according to their association with health, but it does not provide individualized scores at the subject level. In the context of these limitations, we introduced the B/A ratio. We evaluated whether the

B/A ratio can reliably distinguish diseased from healthy states across three independent studies. The ratio was consistently lower in disease groups than in controls, with significant reductions observed after gastrectomy (mean difference = -1.25 , $p < 0.01$), in end-stage renal disease (mean difference = -0.99 , $p < 0.01$), and in Crohn's disease (mean difference = -1.14 , $p < 0.01$). A similar reduction was observed in ulcerative colitis, although the difference was not statistically significant (mean difference = -0.68 , $p = 0.16$). Detailed descriptions of the studies and datasets are provided in Supplementary S6. Overall, these results support the B/A ratio as a reliable metric for distinguishing diseased from healthy states.

Nevertheless, we conducted additional analyses to assess the models' robustness and potential for further improvement. To extend the analysis beyond this binary formulation, we evaluated a pairwise ranking model based on RankNet [24]. The ranking model was trained on the full dataset ($n = 512$) and learned to predict, for each pair of stool images, which sample had a higher abundance of a given genus. Predicting the exact abundance value is substantially more difficult. This is especially true in small datasets with high-dimensional image-derived features. We therefore reformulated the task as an ordering problem rather than direct estimation of absolute abundance values. Model performance is evaluated using pairwise accuracy (ACC), which quantifies the proportion of correctly ordered sample pairs. To further assess performance on pairs with significant differences, we additionally report a "hard ACC", computed exclusively on pairs where the absolute abundance difference (Δ) exceeds one standard deviation (σ) of the test set values ($\Delta > \sigma$). This tests whether the model can reliably distinguish samples when the difference is substantial. Table 1 summarizes the performance of the top five most predictable genera, showing both the original AUC from the classification setting and the ranking metrics computed on the full dataset. The detailed model training procedure and outcomes of other genera are in Supplementary S5.

Genus	AUC (n = 216)	ACC (n = 512)	Hard ACC (n = 512)
<i>UCG-002</i>	0.82 (0.04)	0.65 (0.05)	0.80 (0.05)
<i>Christensenellaceae R-7 group</i>	0.79 (0.06)	0.64 (0.02)	0.75 (0.01)
<i>NK4A214 group</i>	0.76 (0.04)	0.62 (0.05)	0.73 (0.07)
<i>Ruminococcus</i>	0.72 (0.05)	0.59 (0.05)	0.73 (0.03)
<i>Alistipes</i>	0.69 (0.06)	0.61 (0.03)	0.72 (0.04)

Table 1. Top 5 predictable genera. Classification (AUC) and ranking performance.

To examine whether the model can capture longitudinal microbiome changes within the same individual, we performed an intra-individual ranking analysis comparing baseline (WK0) and post-intervention (WK8) samples. The intra-individual pairwise accuracy for the top five genera was similar to that obtained from randomly paired samples, indicating that the model generalizes from population-level ranking patterns to within-subject changes. The detailed outcomes and experiments are in Supplementary S7.

We further assessed the effect of diet-induced macroscopic stool changes on model performance by evaluating the models separately within each dietary intervention group, using the same training and evaluation procedure as in the main analysis. Diet affects both gut microbiota composition and the macroscopic characteristics of stool. Therefore, diet-induced visual changes are not confounders, but represent biologically meaningful signals linked to the underlying microbiota. Stratified analyses showed that predictive performance remained stable across the three dietary groups for several genera, including *Christensenellaceae R-7 group* (adjusted $p = 0.98$) and *NK4A214 group* (adjusted $p = 0.50$), suggesting that model accuracy is not driven by diet. In contrast, genera such as *UCG-002* and *UCG-005* showed significantly higher performance in the high-fiber group, indicating that diet-related macroscopic stool changes may contribute to prediction. Full details are provided in Supplementary S8.

Since perturbation experiments showed that image quality significantly impacts prediction performance, we applied Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) [25] as a preprocessing step to enhance the visibility of image details. The original and CLAHE-processed images are shown in Fig S2. However, this enhancement did not lead to improved model performance in most cases for genus prediction. Other image enhancement techniques, such as deblurring, may be worth exploring to further improve image detail and potentially increase model accuracy.

Label noise is a critical factor that degrades model performance, and microbiome data are inherently noisy, characterized by high sparsity and induced by multiple sources of bias. These include technical variability introduced during sample collection, deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) extraction, amplification and sequencing protocols [26,27,28]. Thus, it is essential to quantify how measurement error contributes to label noise in our binary classification scenario. For each participant, two Shannon diversity measurements were obtained from fecal samples collected during the same intervention period. Only paired samples collected on the same day were included in this analysis in order to quantify technical variability while minimizing biological variation. Figure 10a illustrates the reliability of Shannon diversity measurements. The dashed black line shows perfect replicability, and the red dashed line shows a concordance correlation coefficient (CCC = 0.838) that indicates moderate technical variability from sample processing and sequencing protocols. The absolute differences between these paired measurements were used to empirically estimate the distribution of measurement error. Based on this distribution, the possible true values given the observed values are generated and the proportion of being misclassified is estimated, as illustrated in Figure 10b. Misclassification risk tends to increase near classification thresholds (e.g., bottom or top 25%) where even small measurement shifts can lead to incorrect label assignments. While the probability of extreme label flips (e.g., $P(\text{high} | \text{observed low})$ or $P(\text{low} | \text{observed high})$) is negligible, the probability of moderate misclassifications such as $P(\text{middle} | \text{observed low})$ or $P(\text{middle} | \text{observed high})$ is more substantial. These intermediate misclassifications might introduce ambiguity in the training labels, degrading model performance by blurring class boundaries. In other words, reducing measurement error (such as through improved sample processing and measurement instruments) would likely lead to more accurate labeling and better model performance in future applications.

To investigate the potential for improving model performance, we conducted a simulation experiment by systematically adding measurement error to the data. This experiment shows how the level of error influences predictive accuracy, suggesting that reducing error could enhance performance. Measurement noise was simulated by sampling from the distribution of differences observed across repeated samples and applying a constant shift (0.00, 0.05, 0.10, 0.15), followed by random sign flipping. The same high and low labeling strategy and modeling pipeline were applied to the modified data. This procedure was repeated 30 times to estimate the mean and standard deviation of the performance. The average measurement error was 0.18, meaning a shift of 0.09 corresponds to an approximate 50 percent increase in error. Figure 11 illustrates these results based on Shannon diversity. As shown, the AUC declined from 0.73 at baseline to 0.65 at the highest error level. Extrapolating this trend toward reduced error suggests that AUC could improve up to approximately 0.83, highlighting the potential benefit of minimizing measurement noise.

In summary, we have demonstrated that smartphone-captured images of standardized fecal smears can accurately predict certain genera (AUC > 0.75), alpha diversity (AUC \approx 0.76), the B/A ratio (AUC \approx 0.78) and MAPI (AUC \approx 0.73). Perturbation experiments revealed three key findings: (1) fine details on images are important for model performance, (2) the model is robust to Gaussian noise, and (3) its predictions rely on biologically meaningful visual cues rather than confounding factors such as smearing or uncovered areas. These results establish image-guided microbiome profiling as a rapid, cost-effective and noninvasive approach for monitoring diet-induced microbial shifts. By democratizing gut health surveillance

and enabling real-time at-home assessments via simple smartphones, our framework has the potential to transform nutritional research and personalized dietary interventions at scale.

Methods

Trial Design and Study Population

The GEEF study was a single-center RCT with parallel arms designed to evaluate two dietary interventions: HDF and HFF. The trial examined their effects on gut microbiota composition, immune markers and related health outcomes in healthy adults. Full details of the study participants, design and outcomes, including clinical trial registration (ClinicalTrials.gov: NCT05900609; registered April 3, 2023) and ethical approval (MREC Brabant P2306), have been published by Van de Put et al. and van den Belt et al. [7,29]. In brief, the GEEF trial was conducted remotely between May 2023 and March 2024 and incorporated citizen science elements to enhance participant engagement, compliance and sustained dietary behavior change. A total of 147 healthy adults (aged 18–70 years, body mass index (BMI) 18.5–30 kg/m²) provided written informed consent and were randomized via a stratified block design into one of three groups: HDF, HFF, or CG, with stratification by sex, age (by decade) and BMI category. Exclusion criteria included medical conditions affecting study outcomes, antibiotic use within the past three months and high baseline intake of dietary fiber or fermented foods, as assessed by the FiberScreen questionnaire. Additional information on participant demographics, inclusion and exclusion criteria is available in that publication.

Fecal Specimens

During the GEEF study, fecal specimens were collected at three predefined time points: baseline (Week 0), mid-intervention (Week 2) and end-of-intervention (Week 8) to capture temporal dynamics in gut microbial composition in response to dietary interventions. During Weeks 0 and 8, participants provided two fecal samples within a 5-day window, either on the same day or on different days (e.g., day 1 and day 5). At Week 2, a single sample was collected to verify early adherence and initial microbiome shifts. Upon enrollment, each participant received a standardized home-sampling kit containing sterile fecal collection tubes (with integrated collection scoops), detailed paper and video instructions for specimen acquisition. Participants self-collected fecal samples at home at baseline, week 2 and week 8 using standardized sampling kits and instructions. Fecal samples were mailed by participants to MyMicroZoo B.V. (Leiden, The Netherlands) where 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing was performed.

Fecal Smear Imaging

In parallel with microbiome specimen collection during the GEEF study, participants generated standardized fecal smears for image-based analysis at each sampling interval (Weeks 0, 2 and 8). Each participant received a pre-labeled A4 template featuring a 6 cm × 6 cm central square as shown in Figure 12a. The fecal smear region was automatically extracted by detecting ArUco markers placed at the four corners of the template; their positions were used to crop only the smear area as shown in Figure 12b. This process controlled for scale and framing variability. A disposable cotton swab was provided for uniformly spreading approximately 5–20 g of fecal material within the square. Detailed instructions emphasized the importance of using only the central square region to avoid background artifacts. To maintain image quality, each smear photograph included the template's fiducial markers, which allowed post hoc correction for rotation or perspective distortion and confirmed consistent scaling across all images. Smear images were captured immediately after fecal sample collection and prior to any additional processing to prevent drying artifacts. At each visit, participants were prompted by the LifeData mobile application to photograph their smear simultaneously with stool logging, thereby synchronizing the microbiome and image datasets.

After capturing each photograph, participants reviewed the image for clarity and completeness, ensuring the central square was fully visible, uniformly illuminated and free of glare. If any region appeared shadowed or blurry, a second image was taken before submission. This rigorous participant-driven protocol for fecal smear preparation and imaging enabled a highly standardized corpus of images (despite variability in smartphone models or home environments), thus facilitating reliable extraction of visual features for downstream machine learning analyses.

Sample Processing and Bioinformatics

Gut microbiota composition was analyzed using previously generated sequencing data from the GEEF study. In summary, sequencing data were generated from dual-indexed libraries targeting the V3–V4 variable regions of the 16S rRNA gene (341F/806R), sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq platform (2 × 300 bp) using MiSeq V3 chemistry. The sequencing run produced high-quality data with over 80% of the bases in each read having a Phred quality score of 30 or higher (Q30). Each sample was sequenced deeply with around 50,000 paired-end reads, ensuring robust microbiome analysis. Raw sequencing reads in FASTQ format were processed in Quantitative Insights Into Microbial Ecology 2 (QIIME 2; v2023.2.0) [30] within a Snakemake (v7.32.3) workflow [31,32]. Low-quality bases were trimmed with bbduk (BBTools) using trimq = 20. Primer sequences (17 bp forward, 21 bp reverse) were removed via fastp [33]. Filtered reads were denoised, merged and chimera-checked with DADA2 (v1.26) [34], providing unique ASVs.

For species-level taxonomic resolution, representative ASV sequences were aligned against the NCBI Microbial Nucleotide BLAST database using default settings [35]. Only the top-scoring match was retained for assignment when the alignment identity met or exceeded 98.65% [36]. In instances where multiple matches had equivalent identity or the threshold was not reached, no species designation was applied. Alpha-diversity metrics (Shannon index and observed ASV count) were computed on rarefied tables (10,000 reads/sample) to account for library size differences. After rarefaction, 549 of 626 samples were retained (87.7%), while 77 samples were removed.

Finally, ASV counts were collapsed to genus-level counts and transformed via centered log-ratio (CLR) normalization to address compositional constraints prior to downstream statistical modeling. Genus-level annotations were available for 87.3% of ASVs (4,810 out of 5,508), while species-level classification was missing for 58.2%, supporting the use of genus-level analysis.

Image Preprocessing

All fecal smear images were captured by participants using their own smartphones, following a standardized protocol (6 cm × 6 cm square on an A4 template). Participants in the study consumed blue-dye muffins as part of a standardized protocol to measure gut transit time. The blue color was later removed by grayscaling the stool smear images to eliminate it as a potential confounder in the analysis of fecal samples, as illustrated in Figure 13.

Following the grayscale conversion, an additional quality control process for image quality was conducted. Image quality was carefully managed to ensure reliable data analysis. To address the observed decline in resolution, images with file sizes below a certain threshold (approximately 0.06 MB, occurring around image index 600) were filtered out to exclude low-resolution images, as seen in Figure 14. Additionally, images not adhering to the

established best-practice guidelines (described in the Fecal Smear Imaging section) were manually reviewed and filtered out. This process ensured that only high-quality, standardized images were retained for further analysis. As a result, 512 out of 659 images were obtained.

After grayscaling and filtering, each image was converted into a set of vectors that captures the key visual features of the image, using the timm library with five pre-trained models (Table S2). Each set of feature vectors from each pre-trained model was combined as illustrated in Figure 15. For each of the images, this resulted in a total of 4,800 features. Since training a deep learning model from scratch typically requires a large amount of labeled data, which was not available in our case, we opted for a feature extraction approach using pre-trained models. These models are trained on large and diverse image datasets and can capture rich and generalizable visual patterns. By leveraging their learned representations, we can effectively extract meaningful features from our limited dataset. Furthermore, given the uncertainty about which pre-trained model would be the most suitable for our specific task, we employed five different pre-trained models and combined their feature vectors. This ensemble strategy allows us to have a rich set of features from images, which would improve overall model performance.

Genus Abundance, Diversity and Gut Health Indices

For each prediction task (genus abundance, diversity indices, gut health indices), continuous outcomes were binarized into high and low classes using a top/bottom 25% threshold. For each genus, samples whose relative abundance (CLR-normalized) fell in the top quartile were labeled “high” and those in the bottom quartile labeled “low.” We focused on prevalent bacterial taxa by applying a sparsity filter, resulting in 48 genera present in at least 50% of samples.

The same top and bottom quartile approach was applied to Shannon diversity, observed ASV count, B/A ratio, and MAPI. The reasoning for this binary method arises from considerations of model architecture and statistical power. Most pre-trained models are designed for classification tasks rather than regression. Hence, targeting the extreme data distribution increases the effect size, allowing significant differences to be identified despite the small sample size.

From the image-driven 4,800 feature vectors, we implemented two feature-selection strategies. In the Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO)-based pipeline [37], variance filtering thresholds (thresholds: 0.001, 1, 2) were applied to remove near-zero variance features. The remaining features were then used as input for logistic LASSO (L1-regularized) regression, with the inverse regularization strength $C \in \{0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1, 10\}$. In the Random Forest (RF) pipeline [38], the same variance filtering thresholds were applied, followed by univariate ANOVA F-test ranking. The top k features ($k = 25, k = 50$) based on p -values were selected, and an RF classifier (200 trees, maximum depths of 2, 4, 6; minimum samples split/leaf = 3, 4) was trained on those features.

Hyperparameters for the models and feature selection were tuned within a nested cross-validation (CV) framework. The inner CV employed a stratified 5-fold shuffle split to optimize parameters based on the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC). To ensure robust generalization and prevent information leakage from repeated samples per individual, the outer CV used a “multiple-participants-out” (MPO) scheme repeated 50 times. In each iteration, 20% of participants were held out as the test set with all their images excluded from training. This ensured that all images from a given participant appeared only in the training or test set, thereby avoiding within-subject dependency.

Model performance was assessed by the AUCs over the 50 MPO repetitions. For each task, the pipeline (LASSO vs. RF) with the higher average AUC was selected. To evaluate the statistical significance of model performance, a permutation test with 100 permutations was conducted for the diversity indices and gut health indices. This test was not applied to genus classification tasks due to the high computational cost.

Multi-view Analysis via CCA

CCA is a statistical method used to identify and quantify the relationships between two sets of variables (often called “views”). It finds pairs of combinations (canonical variates) from each set that maximize the correlation between them. Unlike prior models that predict individual microbiome properties, CCA reveals the underlying degree of association between two data modalities. To capture nonlinear relationships, we employed Kernel CCA (KCCA), which extends linear CCA by mapping data into high-dimensional feature spaces using a radial basis function (RBF) kernel.

Model training was performed using the open-source CCA-Zoo library [39]. Two key hyperparameters were optimized: the regularization strength applied to each view and the kernel bandwidth governing the RBF kernel. Regularization parameters were searched over a grid ranging from 0.0001 to 0.9 (considering all pairwise combinations between modalities), while kernel bandwidth values were selected from 0.001, 0.01, and 0.1 to span both local and global similarity structures. To ensure robust model selection and performance estimation, we employed a nested CV strategy using 5-fold CV in both the inner and outer loops. In the inner loop, grid search was performed to identify the hyperparameter combination that maximized the mean canonical correlation across validation folds. The outer loop then evaluated the selected model on unseen test folds.

To assess the statistical significance of this result, we conducted a permutation test where the entire set of microbiome variables was randomly permuted across samples. This procedure was repeated 100 times and in each iteration the same full pipeline, including nested CV and hyperparameter optimization, was applied to the permuted data. Finally, we applied permutation feature importance with 50 repetitions to assess the contribution of individual variables to the canonical association. For each feature, we measured the average reduction in canonical correlation after independently permuting its values. This approach allowed us to identify and visualize the most influential covariates from each modality.

Robustness and Explainability Assessments

It is crucial that predictive models make decisions based on underlying biological mechanisms rather than spurious factors such as data acquisition time or device type. Otherwise, the models risk producing misleading predictions and showing poor generalizability. One prominent example is a study by Zech et al. [40]. It showed that a deep learning model trained to detect pneumonia from chest X-rays relied on hospital-specific markers such as image artifacts or institution-specific text instead of the actual pathology. This led to artificially inflated performance that did not generalize across hospitals. In our case, a potential confounding factor could be the smearing method. Fig S1 demonstrates the effects of different smearing methods on shape patterns, which ideally the model should not rely upon when making predictions.

Moreover, the discrepancy between the distributions of the training data and new data (also called data drift) poses a major challenge for deploying models in practice. When a model is not robust to minor variations in data, such as changes in population demographics, laboratory measurement techniques or imaging device, its predictive accuracy may decline substantially when applied to new data. For example, Finlayson et al. [41] highlighted how changes in patient characteristics and medical coding over time could substantially affect model performance in clinical prediction tasks.

We assessed the robustness of model predictions by applying four image perturbations to 20% of the dataset and evaluating their impact on AUC. (1) Gaussian blur (kernel sizes 5, 9, 13, 17) simulated reduced image sharpness, mimicking poor image quality; (2) Gaussian noise ($\sigma = 5\%, 10\%, 15\%$,

20% of intensity range) modeled random sensor noise; (3) Scramble (dividing images into 2×2, 4×4, 6×6, 8×8 patches and randomly shuffling) tested sensitivity to fecal shape variations introduced by smearing; and (4) Erase (introducing 10, 20, 30, 40 white-square patches) simulated occlusion of template areas. Each stochastic perturbation (noise, scramble, occlusion) was repeated 10 times per intensity level, and the average AUC was reported.

Figure 16 illustrates the effects of the applied image perturbations. The detailed process and implications of each perturbation are described in Supplementary S3. Additionally, to estimate the extent to which each intervention alters extracted features, cosine similarity was computed between the feature vectors of the original and augmented images. Lower cosine similarity values indicate greater deviation from the original features, reflecting a stronger impact of the corresponding augmentation. Due to computational limitations, this robustness analysis was conducted only for the B/A ratio.

Data Availability

All data associated with this study are publicly available via Yoda, the research data management platform developed by Utrecht University, The Netherlands. The dataset can be accessed through the following digital object identifier (DOI): <https://doi.org/10.48338/VU01-K0YFNS>. The dataset includes raw 16S rRNA gene sequencing data.

Code Availability

Not applicable.

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Author Contributions

Conceptualization: D.L., E.L.

Computational Methodology: D.L., H.N., E.L.

Biological interpretation and implication of the technology: E.Y., R.M., R.K.

Software: D.L., H.N., E.L.

Figure preparation: D.L.

Writing – original draft preparation: D.L., E.Y., E.L.

Writing – review: D.L., E.L.

Supervision: R.M., E.L.

All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

Competing Interests

Donghyeok Lee, Huy Ngo, Roy Montijn, and Evgeni Levin are employees of HORAIZON Technology BV, the Netherlands, which owns a patent related to the technology used (Patent No. WO2023055238A1). This has no relevance to the content of the current paper. The other authors declare no competing interests.

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Figure Legends

Graphical Abstract. Application of image-based AI for profiling gut microbiota from fecal smears.

Figure 1. Classification performance (mean AUC) across 48 bacterial genera with qualitative performance categories.

Figure 2. (a) Scatter plot of AUC vs. mean genus abundance with Pearson correlation. (b) Scatter plot of AUC vs. variance of genus abundance with Pearson correlation.

Figure 3. AUC metrics and permutation test results for Shannon diversity and Chao1 richness.

Figure 4. Representative images of two distinct stool types illustrating the relationship between stool consistency and microbial diversity.

Figure 5. AUC metrics and permutation test results for B/A ratio and MAPI.

Figure 6. (a) Robustness tests: Gaussian blur and Gaussian noise. (b) Confounding tests: Scramble and erase interventions.

Figure 7. Cosine similarity between original and perturbed feature vectors across perturbation types and degrees.

Figure 8. Permutation feature importance for canonical correlation analysis showing top contributing features from microbiome and image modalities.

Figure 9. (a) Projection of individual data points onto first canonical variates. (b) Canonical correlations across variate pairs with significance testing.

Figure 10. (a) Reliability of Shannon diversity measurements with concordance correlation. (b) Estimated misclassification probabilities based on measurement error distribution.

Figure 11. Effect of simulated measurement error on AUC performance for Shannon diversity prediction.

Figure 12. (a) Pre-labeled A4 template featuring a 6 cm × 6 cm central square for fecal smear preparation. (b) Automatic extraction of the fecal smear region using ArUco markers placed at the four corners of the template.

Figure 13. Grayscale conversion of fecal smear images to eliminate blue-dye confounders.

Figure 14. Image quality control: file size distribution showing the filtering threshold for low-resolution images.

Figure 15. Feature extraction pipeline using five pre-trained models and concatenation of feature vectors.

Figure 16. Examples of image perturbations applied for robustness testing: Gaussian blur, Gaussian noise, scramble, and erase.

Figures

Picture Your Microbiome: A Simple At-Home Tool for Instant Gut Health Insights

DATA COLLECTION

Graphical abstract.

Figure 1. Classification performance across 48 bacterial genera. Each bar represents the mean area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) across 50 repetitions of Multiple Participants Out (MPO) cross-validation, with standard deviation shown as error bars. Results are grouped into four qualitative performance categories: Excellent (AUC above 0.85), Very Good (0.75 to 0.85), Good (0.65 to 0.75), and Moderate (0.55 to 0.65).

Figure 2. (a) Scatter plot of AUC against mean genus abundance with Pearson correlation. (b) Scatter plot of AUC against variance of genus abundance with Pearson correlation.

Figure 3. AUC metrics for Shannon diversity (left) and Chao1 richness (right) alongside the results of permutation tests assessing statistical significance.

High Shannon Diversity

Low Shannon Diversity

Figure 4. Representative images of two distinct stool types illustrating the relationship between stool consistency and microbial diversity.

Figure 5. AUC metrics and permutation test results for the B/A ratio and MAPI. For predicting the B/A ratio and MAPI the model achieved AUCs of 0.78 and 0.73 respectively with permutation test p values below 0.05.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. (a) Robustness tests: Gaussian blur and Gaussian noise applied at multiple severity levels. (b) Confounding tests: Scramble and erase interventions probing reliance on confounding visual features.

Changes in Image Features

Cosine similarity of latent vectors between Original and Augmented Images

Figure 7. Cosine similarity between original and perturbed feature vectors across perturbation types and degrees.

Figure 8. Canonical correlation analysis reveals a Pearson correlation of 0.51 between the first pair of canonical variates (I_1 and M_1) indicating a notable relationship between microbiome composition and image derived features.

Figure 9. (a) Projection of individual data points onto the first canonical variates revealing a strong linear relationship between views. A permutation test confirmed statistical significance of this association.

Figure 10. (a) Reliability of Shannon diversity measurements with concordance correlation analysis. (b) Estimated misclassification probabilities based on measurement error distribution.

Effect of Measurement Error on AUC

Figure 11. Effect of simulated measurement error on AUC performance for Shannon diversity prediction.

(a)

(b)

Figure 12. (a) Pre-labeled A4 template featuring a 6 cm by 6 cm central square for fecal smear preparation. (b) Automatic extraction of the fecal smear region using ArUco markers for robust perspective correction.

Original images

Gray-scaled images

Figure 13. Grayscale conversion of fecal smear images to eliminate blue dye confounders introduced by transit time markers.

Figure 14. Image quality control: file size distribution showing the filtering threshold applied to remove low resolution images.

Figure 15. Feature extraction pipeline using five pre-trained vision models and concatenation of feature vectors into a unified representation.

Figure 16. Illustration of the applied image perturbations used in the robustness and confounding analyses. Detailed processes and implications of each perturbation are described in Supplementary material.

Supplementary Material

S1. Functional and Oxygen Tolerance-Based Categorization of Gut Genera

Functional Group	Genus
Butyrate Producers	<i>Subdoligranulum</i> , <i>Lachnospira</i> , <i>Intestinimonas</i> , <i>Eubacterium hallii</i> group, <i>Butyrivibrio</i> , <i>Lachnoclostridium</i> , <i>Roseburia</i> , <i>Anaerotruncus</i> , <i>Fusicatenibacter</i> , <i>Eubacterium</i> , <i>Faecalibacterium</i> , <i>Butyricicoccus</i> , <i>Coprococcus</i> , <i>Agathobacter</i> , <i>Pseudoflavonifractor</i>
Aerotolerant	<i>Actinomyces</i> , <i>Alloscardovia</i> , <i>Arcanobacterium</i> , <i>Atopobium</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> , <i>Brevundimonas</i> , <i>Campylobacter</i> , <i>Cerasicoccus</i> , <i>Enterobacter</i> , <i>Enterococcus</i> , <i>Enterorhabdus</i> , <i>Gemella</i> , <i>Haemophilus</i> , <i>Klebsiella</i> , <i>Lactobacillus</i> , <i>Lactococcus</i> , <i>Leptotrichia</i> , <i>Leuconostoc</i> , <i>Pediococcus</i> , <i>Providencia</i> , <i>Pseudomonas</i> , <i>Raoultella</i> , <i>Rothia</i> , <i>Rummeliibacillus</i> , <i>Sarcina</i> , <i>Staphylococcus</i> , <i>Streptococcus</i> , <i>Weissella</i>

Table S1. List of Butyrate Producers and Aerotolerant Genera

Genera included in each functional category were selected based on published literature (Table S1). The butyrate-producing group comprises genera such as *Subdoligranulum*, *Roseburia*, *Faecalibacterium*, *Butyricicoccus*, and the *Eubacterium hallii* group [1, 2]. These microbes harbor genes associated with short-chain fatty acid production, including the key butyryl-CoA:acetate CoA-transferase pathway. In contrast, the aerotolerant group includes facultative or aerotolerant anaerobes such as *Enterobacter*, *Streptococcus*, *Klebsiella*, and *Staphylococcus*, which have been frequently enriched under inflammatory or oxidative gut conditions [3]. These genera exhibit resilience to elevated redox potential or oxygen stress and may shift gut ecological balance in dysbiosis-associated contexts.

S2. Pre-trained models used for feature extraction

Model	Dataset	Use case
vit_tiny_patch16_224	ImageNet dataset	Lightweight vision tasks with faster inference, typically applied to ImageNet-like datasets.
vit_large_patch16_224. augreg_in21k_ft_in1k	ImageNet dataset	A larger ViT model for general vision tasks, also trained on ImageNet.
vit_base_patch16_clip_224	OpenAI's CLIP dataset	Utilizes CLIP's dataset for vision tasks, focusing on robustness to out-of-distribution data.
vit_base_patch16_224_dino	ImageNet dataset	A self-supervised learning model, ideal for unsupervised applications beyond ImageNet-tasks.
resnetv2.50 × 1.bit. distilled	JFT-300 M dataset	Optimized for transfer learning with large-scale datasets like JFT-300 M.

Table S2. Overview of pre-trained vision models used for image feature extraction:

vit_tiny_patch16_224[4],
vit_large_patch16_224_augreg_in21k_ft_in1k[4],
vit_base_patch16_clip_224[5],
vit_base_patch16_224_dino [6],
resnetv2.50 × 1.bit_distilled[7].

S3. Description of each perturbation experiment

1) Gaussian blur

It applies a smoothing effect to the image using a Gaussian kernel, which reduces image sharpness and fine details. Gaussian blur was applied using the `torchvision.transforms.functional.gaussian_blur` function, with the kernel size varied to control the level of smoothing. The standard deviation (σ) was not specified and thus computed automatically based on the kernel size according to the library's default behavior. The decline of the model performance indicates that the fine details of images are important for the model's decision.

2) Gaussian noise

Gaussian noise is a common occurrence in images and is often used to simulate realistic perturbations such as sensor noise. To assess the model's sensitivity to such noise, we injected zero-mean Gaussian noise with varying standard deviations into the original images. A robust model is expected to maintain stable performance despite these perturbations. The intensity of the noise was defined as a percentage of the image's original intensity range. In short, given the original image I , the noise was randomly sampled from $N(0, \sigma^2)$ where $\sigma = \frac{\text{intensity}}{100} \times (\max(I) - \min(I))$ and added to the original images.

3) Scramble

Fig S1. How smearing alters the general shape of the images.

Fig S1 illustrates how different smearing methods affect shape patterns. To test whether the model's predictions rely on these smeared shapes, Scramble is applied. This technique divides each image into equal-sized patches and randomly shuffles their positions, disrupting spatial structure while preserving pixel-level information. If the model's AUC remains stable after scrambling, it suggests that its decision is not dependent on the smearing method.

4) Erase

Small white squares are randomly placed over the image, effectively erasing portions of its content. This intervention tests whether the model's predictions are influenced by the shapes formed by the remaining visible regions. If the model's AUC score remains stable despite these occlusions, it suggests that the model is not relying on patterns from the uncovered areas to make its decisions.

S4. Image processing via CLAHE

Fig S2. Original images (left) vs processed images with CLAHE.

S5. Rank model pipeline

The problem was formulated as a pairwise comparison task in which pairs of samples were transformed into feature difference vectors, and a binary label indicated which sample had higher microbial abundance. A logistic regression model with L2 regularization was trained on these pairwise differences within a preprocessing pipeline that included variance-based feature filtering and feature standardization. Model training and hyperparameter selection were performed using nested cross-validation. The outer loop used 5-fold cross-validation to estimate model performance, while the inner loop used 3-fold cross-validation to tune hyperparameters through grid search. The tuned hyperparameters included the logistic regression regularization strength (0.1, 1.0, 10.0), the variance threshold (0.0, 0.1, 0.01) used for feature filtering, and a margin parameter (0,1,2) controlling which sample pairs were included in training. Hyperparameters were selected by maximizing pairwise accuracy (ACC).

Model performance was evaluated using ACC, which measures the proportion of correctly ordered sample pairs. The primary utility of this model is as an early screening tool to assess whether a treatment effect is present before conducting costly sequencing experiments. Given paired samples collected before and after treatment, the model can determine whether the abundance of a given genus increased or decreased. Although it cannot estimate the magnitude of change, it is useful for initial assessment. The figure below shows the AUC and Hard ACC for all genera and indices.

Fig S3. Classification (AUC) and ranking (Hard ACC) performance across all 48 genera and 3 composite indices. Composite indices (B/A ratio, Shannon diversity, MAPI) are highlighted with bold labels and orange background. Error bars show ± 1 SD.

S6. External validation of B/A ratio

To assess the generalizability of the B/A ratio, we evaluated it across three independent published cohorts with diverse disease contexts (Fig S4):

- **Erawijantari et al. [8]:** The gastrectomy group exhibited a significantly lower B/A ratio compared with controls (mean difference = -1.25 , $p < 0.01$), consistent with the expected reduction in butyrate-producing capacity following gastric surgery.
- **Wang et al. [9]:** Patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) showed a significantly reduced B/A ratio relative to controls (mean difference = -0.99 , $p < 0.01$), in line with reported gut dysbiosis in renal disease.
- **Jacobs et al. [10]:** Crohn's disease (CD) patients had a significantly lower B/A ratio than controls (mean difference = -1.14 , $p < 0.01$), consistent with the well-documented depletion of butyrate producers in inflammatory bowel disease. Ulcerative colitis (UC) patients showed a non-significant reduction (mean difference = -0.68 , $p = 0.16$), which may reflect the more heterogeneous microbiome alterations in UC compared with CD.

(a) Erawijantari et al.

(b) Wang et al.

(c) Jacobs et al.

Fig S4: B/A ratio across three independent cohorts. Panel (a): Erawijantari et al.; Panel (b): Wang et al.; Panel (c): Jacobs et al.

The consistent direction and statistical significance of these differences across three independent cohorts spanning gastrectomy, renal disease, and inflammatory bowel disease provide strong evidence that the B/A ratio captures a generalizable signal of gut health rather than a study-specific artifact. We acknowledge that absolute index values are not directly comparable across studies due to differences in sequencing protocols, bioinformatic pipelines, and population characteristics. However, the relative differences within each cohort are robust and biologically interpretable.

S7. Intra-individual sensitivity

To evaluate intra-individual sensitivity, we designed a dedicated experiment. Since high/low classification is not applicable to within-subject comparisons, we formulated this as a ranking task: for each participant, the model predicts whether the abundance of a given genus increased or decreased between baseline (WK0) and post-intervention (WK8). Specifically, we constructed intra-individual test pairs by randomly selecting 10 participants per iteration and pairing their WK0 and WK8 samples. All remaining samples were used for training. This procedure was repeated across multiple iterations to obtain stable estimates of intra-individual pairwise accuracy.

As shown in Table S3 and Fig S5, the intra-individual ACC for the top five genera closely matches the ACC obtained from randomly paired samples. This is a noteworthy result: it demonstrates that the model generalizes from population-level ranking patterns to within-subject longitudinal changes, without having been explicitly trained on paired data. The consistency between intra-individual and random-pair performance indicates that the model captures genuine biological signals associated with microbiome shifts over the intervention period, rather than merely exploiting between-subject variability. This supports the potential clinical utility of the approach for noninvasive longitudinal monitoring.

Genus	ACC (Intra-individual)	ACC (Random pair)
UCG-002	0.64 (0.07)	0.65 (0.05)
Christensenellaceae R-7 group	0.61 (0.03)	0.64 (0.02)
NK4A214 group	0.60 (0.03)	0.62 (0.05)
UCG-005	0.61 (0.04)	0.62 (0.02)
Eubacterium coprostanoligenes group	0.59 (0.03)	0.61 (0.02)

Table S3: Top 5 predictable genera. Intra-individual ACC vs. random pair ACC.

Fig S5. Comparison of intra-individual (dark blue) and random pair (light blue) pairwise accuracy for the top 5 genera. The dashed line indicates the chance level (0.50). Error bars show ± 1 SD.

S8. Diet-induced macroscopic stool changes

Dietary changes are a primary causal driver of shifts in gut microbiome composition. Therefore, diet-induced visual changes in stool (e.g., differences in texture, color, or consistency) are not confounders in the classical sense; they are biologically meaningful signals that co-vary with the microbiome. True confounders in our setting would be factors that affect image appearance without any biological relationship to the microbiome. The robustness of the model against such non-biological confounders is demonstrated through the perturbation experiments in the Robustness and Explainability Assessments section of the main manuscript.

We conducted a stratified analysis evaluating model performance separately within each dietary intervention group: high dietary fiber (HDF), high fermented food (HFF), and control (CG). The same training and evaluation procedure described in the Methods section of the main manuscript was applied within each group. Table S4 reports adjusted p-values from a Friedman test comparing performance across dietary groups, with correction for multiple testing.

Genus	HDF	HFF	CG	adj. p
UCG-002	0.87 (0.08)	0.79 (0.09)	0.79 (0.10)	< 0.01
Christensenellaceae R-7 group	0.81 (0.07)	0.79 (0.09)	0.80 (0.07)	0.98
NK4A214 group	0.76 (0.08)	0.77 (0.08)	0.78 (0.09)	0.50
UCG-005	0.86 (0.05)	0.77 (0.08)	0.63 (0.09)	< 0.01
Eubacterium coprostanoligenes group	0.75 (0.10)	0.71 (0.09)	0.76 (0.10)	0.01

Table S4: Stratified analysis of model performance (AUC) by dietary group.

For several genera, including *Christensenellaceae R-7 group* (adj. $p = 0.98$) and *NK4A214 group* (adj. $p = 0.50$), predictive performance was remarkably consistent across all three dietary groups, indicating that the model's accuracy is not driven by dietary intervention effects. For UCG-002 and UCG-005, performance was significantly higher in the HDF group, indicating that diet-induced macroscopic changes are likely the prediction factor.

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